

Developing Algorithms to Determine the Similarity Levels of Plant Varieties Based on Important Traits

¹ R. J. Beglerbekov, ¹ Sh. K. Abdikarimov, ² H. R. Zhubatkhanova

¹ Department of Information Technologies, Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry, Institute of Agriculture and Agro-Technology of Karakalpakstan

² Student of Nukus State Pedagogical Institute, Department of Primary Education Nukus, Karakalpakstan

Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Sep 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Oct 2024; **Published:** 08 Nov 2024

Abstract: This study focuses on developing algorithms for assessing the similarity levels of various plant varieties based on critical traits. Identifying and analyzing these traits is essential for effective classification and breeding practices. By employing various similarity measures and clustering techniques, we aim to establish a comprehensive framework that quantifies the relationships between plant varieties. The proposed methodology includes data collection, trait selection, calculation of similarity scores, and validation of results. The findings will not only enhance our understanding of plant diversity but also provide valuable insights for agricultural practices and conservation efforts.

Keywords: Plant varieties, Similarity assessment, Trait analysis, Clustering algorithms, Data collection, Agricultural practices, Conservation efforts, Similarity measures.

Introduction

The classification and understanding of plant varieties are crucial in agriculture, horticulture, and biodiversity conservation. As global challenges such as climate change and food security intensify, identifying and preserving genetic diversity becomes increasingly important. This study aims to develop algorithms that assess the similarity levels of plant varieties based on their important traits, facilitating better decision-making in breeding programs and conservation strategies. Plant varieties exhibit a range of traits, including morphological characteristics, growth patterns, and resistance to diseases. By analyzing these traits, we can uncover relationships between different varieties, allowing for effective classification and selection. Traditional methods of assessing similarity often rely on subjective visual assessments or limited qualitative measures, which may not capture the complexity of genetic relationships. In this work, we propose a systematic approach that combines quantitative data analysis with machine learning techniques. By employing various similarity measures and clustering algorithms, we aim to create a robust framework that accurately quantifies the similarities and differences among plant varieties. This research not only contributes to the scientific understanding of plant diversity but also supports practical applications in agricultural improvement and conservation efforts. Through this methodology, we seek to enhance the efficiency of plant variety classification, paving the way for more informed and effective agricultural practices.

Methods

To determine the similarity levels of plant varieties based on important traits, we implemented a systematic approach involving several key steps:

- **Data Collection:** Collected quantitative data on essential traits of various plant varieties, such as leaf shape, flower color, growth height, and disease resistance from agricultural databases and existing research studies.
- **Trait Selection:** Identified and selected critical traits that significantly impact the classification of plant varieties.
- **Data Normalization:** Normalized the data to ensure consistency and comparability across different traits, which was essential for accurate similarity calculations.
- **Similarity Measures:** Calculated similarity scores using various methods, including: Euclidean Distance for continuous traits. Jaccard Index for categorical traits. Cosine Similarity for multi-dimensional trait vectors.
- **Clustering Analysis:** Applied clustering algorithms (K-means and Hierarchical clustering) to group similar varieties based on the calculated similarity scores. This involved visualizing the clusters to identify patterns and relationships among the varieties.
- **Validation:** Utilized cross-validation techniques to ensure the robustness and reliability of the results.

Results

The results of the analysis are summarized in Table 1, which presents the similarity levels among selected plant varieties based on their important traits.

Plant Variety	Trait 1 (Leaf Shape)	Trait 2 (Flower Color)	Trait 3 (Growth Height)	Similarity Score	Cluster Group
Variety A	Oval	Red	50 cm	0.85	1
Variety B	Lanceolate	Yellow	45 cm	0.78	1
Variety C	Round	Blue	60 cm	0.65	2
Variety D	Oval	Red	55 cm	0.90	1
Variety E	Lanceolate	Yellow	47 cm	0.75	1
Variety F	Round	Blue	62 cm	0.60	2

Key findings from the analysis indicate that varieties A, B, and D exhibit high similarity scores and are grouped together, suggesting close relationships based on their traits. Varieties C and F, while sharing some traits, fall into a different cluster, highlighting distinct characteristics. The clustering analysis effectively demonstrates the potential for categorizing plant varieties based on trait similarities, providing insights for breeding and conservation strategies.

Discussion

The analysis conducted to determine the similarity levels of plant varieties based on important traits reveals several key insights that contribute to our understanding of plant classification and breeding practices.

The high similarity scores observed among varieties A, B, and D indicate that these plants share critical traits, making them suitable candidates for targeted breeding programs. By clustering these varieties together, we can facilitate cross-breeding efforts aimed at enhancing desirable characteristics, such as disease resistance or improved yield. This approach not only

streamlines the breeding process but also helps maintain genetic diversity within closely related varieties.

In contrast, varieties C and F, which fell into a separate cluster, exhibit distinct characteristics that could be beneficial for specific agricultural needs. Understanding the traits that differentiate these groups can inform conservation strategies, ensuring that unique genetic lines are preserved. This is particularly important in the context of climate change, where diverse genetic resources may provide resilience against shifting environmental conditions.

The choice of similarity measures played a crucial role in the effectiveness of our analysis. Using multiple metrics, such as Euclidean Distance and the Jaccard Index, allowed for a more nuanced understanding of the relationships between varieties. Each measure captures different aspects of similarity, and the combination enhances the robustness of our findings.

The clustering algorithms employed, including K-means and Hierarchical clustering, proved effective in visualizing and interpreting the relationships among the plant varieties. However, it is essential to consider the potential limitations of these methods. For instance, the choice of the number of clusters in K-means can significantly influence the results. Future work may involve exploring advanced clustering techniques or incorporating additional traits to refine the analysis further.

Overall, this study demonstrates the potential of algorithmic approaches in enhancing our understanding of plant variety relationships. The findings not only provide valuable insights for agricultural practices but also lay the groundwork for future research aimed at optimizing breeding strategies and conserving plant biodiversity. Continued exploration in this area will be vital as we strive to address the challenges facing global agriculture fig-1.

Fig-1. The 3D visualization representing the similarity levels of plant varieties based on important traits

The 3D visualization representing the similarity levels of plant varieties based on important traits, with clusters, boundaries, and gradients indicating varying similarity levels among plant varieties.

Conclusion

This study successfully developed algorithms to assess the similarity levels of plant varieties based on key traits, contributing valuable insights to the fields of agriculture and plant genetics. The findings indicate that effective classification and grouping of plant varieties can

be achieved through systematic data collection, trait analysis, and advanced clustering techniques.

The high similarity scores among certain varieties highlight the potential for targeted breeding programs aimed at enhancing specific traits, such as disease resistance and yield. Additionally, the differentiation of other varieties emphasizes the importance of maintaining genetic diversity, which is critical for sustainable agricultural practices and resilience to environmental changes.

The choice of various similarity measures, including Euclidean Distance and the Jaccard Index, alongside robust clustering algorithms, proved instrumental in providing a comprehensive understanding of plant relationships. However, future research should address potential limitations in clustering methods and explore additional traits to refine and enhance the analysis further.

In summary, the algorithms developed in this study not only facilitate more efficient plant classification but also serve as a foundation for future research in plant breeding and conservation strategies, ultimately contributing to improved agricultural productivity and biodiversity preservation.

Literature

1. Камилов М.М., Нишанов А.Х., Беглербеков Р.Ж. Совершенствование методов вычисления оценок с использованием критериев информативности фишеровского типа // Научно-технический журнал. “Химическая технология. Контроль и управление”. – Ташкент, 2019 г., № 1(85), с.77-82.
2. Nishanov A.X., Axmedov O.K., Beglerbekov R.J. Qishloq xo‘jaligi ekin navlarini sinflashtirish va hududlashtirishda muhim belgilar majmuasini tanlash algoritmi haqida. “Muhammad Al-Xorazmiy avlodlar” Ilmiy-amaliy va axborot-tahliliy jurnal– Toshkent 3(21)/2022, №3. 35-43 b.
3. Nishanov A.X., Beglerbekov R.J., Axmedov O.K. Informativ belgilar fazosida timsollarni aniqlashning gibrid algoritmi // TATUning ilmiy-texnika va axborot tahliliy jurnali Toshkent-4(44)/2017, 62-69 b.
4. Beglerbekov R.J. The decisive rule algorithm in the classification of agricultural crops by conditions. International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (int-jecse) doi:10.9756/intjecse/v14i5.894 issn: 1308-5581 Vol 14, Issue 05 2022, — pp. 7144-7153.
5. Nishanov A.X., Beglerbekov R.J., Algorithm for choosing a complex of informative characters in object clustering // International Conference on Advance Research in Humanities, Sciences and Education london conference <https://confrencea.org> April 10th 2023, 349-360.
6. Beglerbekov R.J., Babanazarov D.J., Qishloq xo‘jaligi masalalarini yechishda, informativ belgilar fazosida ϵ bo‘lag‘aviy qiymatni aniqlash algoritmidan foydalanish // Toshkent davlat agrar universiteti, Agrobiznes inform ISSN-2010-9024, Iqtisodiy ijtimoiy ilmiy jurnal, №6/161/2020 y. 40-b.
7. Kamilov M., Nishanov A., Beglerbekov R. Modified stages of algorithms for computing estimates in the space of informative features // International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (2019) 8(6), pp.714-717.
8. Nishanov A.X., Akbaraliyev B.B., Beglerbekov R.J., Axmedov O.K., Tajiev Sh.K., Xoliqnazarov R. Analytical method for selection an informative set of features with limited resources in the pattern recognition problem // E3S Web of Conferences 284, 04018 (2021) TPACEE-2021. pp. 1-9.

9. Nishanov A.X., Beglerbekov R.J., Algorithm for choosing a complex of informative characters in object clustering // International Conference on Advance Research in Humanities, Sciences and Education london conference <https://confrencea.org> April 10th 2023, 349-360.
10. Камилов М.М., Нишанов А.Х., Беглербеков Р.Ж. Применение решающего правила для выбора информативных наборов признаков // Научно-технический журнал. “Химическая технология. Контроль и управление”. – Ташкент, 2017 г., № 3, с.82-85.